

Gene Augmentation Therapy for Bestrophinopathies: Targeting BEST1 in the Clinic

Authors: Kenneth C. Fan, MD, MBA¹; Jay S. Pepose, MD, PhD²; Ash Jayagopal, PhD³; Mayur Choudhary, PhD³; Sally Tucker, PhD³; Matthew Weinheimer, OD³; George Magrath, MD, MBA, MS³

Affiliations: ¹Retina Consultants of Texas, Houston, TX, USA

²Pepose Vision Institute, St. Louis, MO, USA

³Opus Genetics, Research Triangle Park, NC, USA

ABSTRACT

The bestrophin-1 (BEST1) gene encodes a calcium-dependent chloride channel, a transmembrane protein critical for the function of the retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) in the eye. Pathogenic variants in BEST1 are the underlying cause for bestrophinopathies, a group of inherited retinal diseases (IRDs) that vary in their pattern of inheritance, clinical appearance, and underlying molecular disease mechanisms. This article focuses on gene therapy strategies to treat Best vitelliform macular dystrophy (BVMD) and autosomal recessive bestrophinopathy (ARB), two conditions for which there are currently no available treatments. Gene therapy represents an attractive strategy to treat BVMD and ARB, in particular gene augmentation, which has a successful track record for treating IRDs. This review examines the clinical diversity of bestrophinopathies and identifies the specific molecular disease mechanism of the pathogenic BEST1 genetic variants as an important parameter for designing future gene therapy strategies. Finally, we highlight the ongoing BIRD-1 (BEST1 Inherited Retinal Diseases) clinical trial as a significant step in translating the gene augmentation strategy into a clinical reality for treating BVMD and ARB.

INTRODUCTION

Gene therapy is poised to revolutionize the treatment of inherited diseases, with the eye leading this development due to its relative immune privilege, anatomical compartmentalization, and surgical accessibility. The transparent ocular media allows for exceptional visualization during retinal surgery, enabling controlled and localized vector delivery to therapeutic targets such as the subretinal space. Moreover, the eye's small volume allows for low vector doses, and the compartmentalized anatomy enables localized therapeutic delivery with minimal systemic exposure [1]. This review focuses on gene therapy strategies for bestrophin-1 (BEST1) related ocular pathologies, specifically Best vitelliform macular dystrophy (BVMD) and autosomal recessive bestrophinopathy (ARB), for which no treatments currently exist. The slow progression of bestrophinopathies, with photoreceptors often remaining viable for decades despite progressive disease, offers a large therapeutic window that makes gene therapy a highly compelling option [2].

Gene augmentation, the introduction of a functional copy of a defective gene, has already demonstrated success in treating inherited retinal diseases (IRDs), most notably with the approval of voretigene neparvovec-rzyl (Luxturna, Spark Therapeutics) by the United States (US) Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and European Medicines Agency (EMA) for biallelic RPE65-mediated Leber congenital amaurosis [3]. This precedent makes gene augmentation particularly promising for ARB, in which biallelic loss-of-function mutations cause complete or near-complete absence of functional BEST1 protein, but supplementation of wildtype BEST1 can restore sufficient channel activity [2].

Importantly, recent functional studies demonstrated that gene augmentation could be effective for the majority of autosomal dominant BVMD cases [4], [5]. The key take-away is that molecular disease mechanisms (loss of function or gain of function at the channel level), rather than the inheritance pattern (dominant versus recessive), should determine the choice of therapeutic approach. Therefore, understanding the molecular disease mechanism of specific BEST1 pathogenic variants is crucial for selecting the appropriate therapeutic strategy and predicting treatment response. This review summarizes the clinical and genetic diversity of bestrophinopathies, examines the molecular mechanisms underlying different BEST1 mutations, and highlights the BIRD-1 (BEST1 Inherited Retinal Diseases) clinical trial, an ongoing Phase 1b/2a study evaluating AAV serotype 2 (AAV2)-mediated BEST1 gene augmentation for both ARB and BVMD [6].

BEST1 Gene Structure and Function

The BEST1 gene provides the instructions for making the BEST1 protein, a crucial component of the retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) cells, where it localizes to the basolateral plasma membrane. Structurally, the gene spans approximately 16 kilobases consisting of 11 exons and is mapped to the 11q13 chromosome [7]. The BEST1 protein is composed of 585 amino acids and functions as a pentamer with five identical subunits that assemble to form a functional calcium-dependent chloride channel (CaCC) [8], [9]. Figure 1 shows the structure of the BEST1 channel.

Functionally, this protein is essential for regulating the ion balance and fluid volume surrounding the photoreceptor cells, which is vital for maintaining the electrical signals required for vision. Mutations in the BEST1 gene disrupt the protein's function, leading to a buildup of deposits rich in oxidized lipids and protein, known as lipofuscin, and fluid beneath the retina. This can cause a group of inherited eye disorders collectively known as bestrophinopathies, the most common of which is BVMD[4], [9], [10].

Image adapted from Amato, A., et al [Saudi J Ophthalmol.](#) 2023; 37(4): 287-295

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the BEST1 channel structure. The ion pore is formed by a pentameric protein structure. Opening of the pore is controlled by the Ca^{2+} clasp, a critical region in BEST1; mutations may negatively affect CaCC function.

Clinical Spectrum of BEST1 Variants

BEST1 variants are inherited in both autosomal dominant and recessive manners and are linked to five distinct clinical phenotypes: ARB, BVMD, autosomal dominant vitreoretinoblastoma (ADVIRC), adult vitelliform macular dystrophy (AVMD), and retinitis pigmentosa (RP) [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16]. BVMD and ARB are the focus of this article.

BVMD is generally considered a rare genetic disease, with an estimated prevalence in the US of 1 in 10,000 individuals and follows a dominant inheritance pattern [17], [18]. BVMD diagnosis is challenging due to significant variability in inter- and intra-familial phenotypes, clinical expression, and patient age of disease onset. ARB is rarer still, affecting approximately 1 in 1 million individuals, and follows an autosomal recessive inheritance pattern. Hence, ARB patients harbor pathogenic biallelic homozygous or compound heterozygous variants in the BEST1 gene [19], [20]. Figure 2 and Figure 3 are representative images of the eyes of patients with ARB and BVMD, respectively.

Figure 2. Fundus photos (left panels), fundus autofluorescence (middle panels), and optical coherence tomography (right panels) of right eye (R) and left eye (L) of patient with autosomal recessive bestrophinopathy (ARB) characterized by multifocal yellow subretinal exudation and subretinal fluid in the macula and perimacular region of both eyes.

Figure 3. Fundus photos (left panels), fundus autofluorescence (middle panels), and optical coherence tomography (right panels) of right eye (R) and left eye (L) of a patient with Best vitelliform macular dystrophy (BVMD) demonstrating a classic "egg-yolk" like appearance in the central macula. A typical central hyperautofluorescence in the region of the vitelliform lesion can be seen.

Clinical Differences between BVMD and ARB

The distinction between dominant and recessive disease phenotypes is determined predominantly by whether the mutant protein undergoes rapid degradation in the endoplasmic reticulum (ER; favoring recessive inheritance) or persists and integrates into pentameric channels via post-ER endo-lysosomal degradation (causing dominant disease) [15]. Autosomal dominant BVMD typically presents in childhood or adolescence with central vision loss and characteristic vitelliform lesions confined to the macula, normal peripheral retina, and reduced electro-oculogram light rise with preserved full-field electroretinogram responses. In contrast, ARB manifests with earlier onset, more severe and widespread retinal involvement extending beyond the macula with subretinal fluid and cystoid changes, variable peripheral retinal abnormalities, and reduced electro-oculogram light rise with frequently abnormal full-field electroretinogram findings indicating more extensive retinal dysfunction [19], [21], [22], [23].

Most bestrophinopathies progress slowly; photoreceptors usually remain viable for decades, thus providing a potentially extended therapeutic window for novel treatment strategies [2]. Thoroughly understanding the gene and protein structure enables the analysis and accurate reclassification of variants of uncertain significance into pathogenic or benign categories. A recent study found 488 different variants listed in Leiden Open Variation Database (LOVD) in 2,205 patients (with a data cut-off on October 29, 2024), and more than 90% of these variants were found to be pathogenic or likely pathogenic [24]. The functional impact of all high-prevalence BEST1 mutations is an area of active research and will be useful for determining therapeutic strategies for gene augmentation.

Molecular Disease Mechanism of Pathogenic BEST1 Variants

The effect of a specific disease-causing variant on protein function, also known as its molecular disease mechanism, is a critical element for tailoring gene therapy strategies. Molecular disease mechanisms of pathogenic variants can be divided into loss-of-function, dominant-negative, and gain-of-function effects [3], [25].

Loss-of-function variants result in impaired or non-functional BEST1 chloride channel through different molecular mechanisms [15]. Similarly, loss of function in recessive bestrophinopathies (ARB) with biallelic mutations results in a complete lack of protein synthesis, the production of a non-functional (amorphic) protein, or the production of a protein with reduced function (hypomorphic) (Figure 4B) [15]. These recessive mutations typically undergo rapid degradation, leaving insufficient functional protein and loss of a functional BEST1 channel [21], [26].

In dominant BVMD, while mutations also result in loss of function at the channel level (reduced chloride currents), the molecular mechanism differs. Dominant BEST1 mutations escape ER-associated degradation and incorporate into pentameric channel complexes with wildtype subunits at roughly equimolar ratios, creating non-functional channels through a dominant-negative mechanism (Figure 4C) rather than simple haploinsufficiency; the latter results from a dose effect, where one functional copy of a gene produces only half the normal amount of protein, which is insufficient for normal function. This distinction is supported by the observation that BEST1 knockout mice (true haploinsufficiency with 50% protein dosage) do not develop a BVMD phenotype [2], [15], [21].

Gain-of-function mutations (Figure 4D) usually have a dominant inheritance pattern and occur due to the protein becoming hypermorphic (i.e., its normal activity is significantly increased) or neomorphic (i.e., it acquires an entirely new biological function)[2]. ADVIRC-associated BEST1 mutations represent gain-of-function variants with constitutively active chloride channels[15], [16].

Image adapted from Haldrup, S., B., et al International Journal of Molecular Sciences. 2025, 26(19), 9421.

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of the molecular disease mechanisms associated with different gene variants. Wildtype alleles/proteins (green), pathogenic alleles/proteins (red), and altered proteins (green spikes) are represented in the different panels as follows: (A) Normal/wildtype gene producing functional protein; **(B) Left:** Biallelic loss-of-function variant typical of ARB, where homozygous or compound heterozygous mutations result in

absent, non-functional, or reduced-function protein. **Right:** Heterozygous carrier state (unaffected); one functional allele produces sufficient protein, demonstrating that haploinsufficiency is not a disease mechanism in BEST1-related disorders; (C) Dominant-negative variant typical of BVMD, where mutant protein incorporates into pentameric channels and interferes with wildtype protein function; (D) Gain-of-function variant typical of ADVIRC, where mutant protein acquires enhanced or novel activity such as constitutively active channel states.

Gene Augmentation Therapeutic Strategy

Molecular mechanisms of disease dictate treatment strategies and are crucial for understanding gene therapy design. The critical insight from recent functional studies is that loss of function at the channel level, regardless of whether it occurs through recessive null mutations or dominant-negative effects, can be rescued by gene augmentation (see Table 1). Multiple different dominant BVMD mutations behave as loss-of-function at the channel level despite their dominant inheritance pattern, and both dominant and recessive loss-of-function mutations have been shown to be rescuable at similar efficacy by gene augmentation via AAV [26]. However, gain-of-function mutations require alternative therapeutic strategies combining gene augmentation with allele-specific knockdown, indicating that mutation-specific mechanisms must be considered when selecting treatment approaches for bestrophinopathies[27].

The key distinction is that the functional outcome (loss-of-function of chloride channel activity), rather than the precise molecular mechanism or inheritance pattern (dominant versus recessive), determines therapeutic response. Gene augmentation works by providing sufficient wildtype BEST1 protein to restore adequate chloride channel activity. In recessive mutations, this compensates for absent or non-functional protein. In dominant mutations with dominant-negative effects, an excess expression of wildtype protein can overcome the deleterious effect of mutant subunits by shifting the equilibrium toward functional pentameric channels[8], [26].

In contrast, gain-of-function bestrophinopathies such as ADVIRC, caused by splicing mutations that produce constitutively active channels with stabilized open-channel states[16], cannot be rescued by gene augmentation alone because adding more wildtype protein does not silence the aberrant channel activity. These cases require more complex strategies combining gene augmentation with allele-specific silencing or gene editing to achieve functional rescue[1], [2], [26], [27].

The preclinical and clinical studies that demonstrate the promise of gene augmentation therapy in ARB and BVMD are listed in Table 1. Most of the groundwork has been done in cell culture and animal models and includes the use of induced pluripotent stem cells

(iPSC). Several studies have demonstrated that by using patient-specific iPSC-RPE “disease-in-a-dish” models, it is possible to predict mutation-specific effects on CaCC activity and responses to gene therapy[28], [29], [30]. These patient-derived iPSC-RPE cells are generated from individual patients carrying specific BEST1 mutations and recapitulate the disease phenotype, allowing functional testing of therapeutic interventions tailored to each mutation[2], [5], [26], [29].

Clinical condition	Inheritance	Delivery vector	Disease Model	Outcome or Objective	Reference
ARB	Autosomal recessive	Baculovirus	Human iPSC-RPE cells	Restored BEST1 CaCC activity (whole-cell patch clamp recording)	Li 2017 [29]
ARB	Autosomal recessive	AAV2	Canine BEST1 disease model	Revision of subretinal detachment and microdetachment. Correction of PR/RPE interface	Guziewicz 2018 [31]
BVMD	Autosomal dominant (loss of function))	AAV2 / Baculovirus	Human iPSC-RPE cells	Restored BEST1 CaCC activity (whole-cell patch clamp recording)	Ji 2019 [26]
BVMD	Autosomal dominant	Lentivirus	Human iPSC-RPE cells	Increased levels of BEST1 protein. Improved RPE function. Restored BEST1 CACC activity (whole-cell patch clamp recording)	Sinha 2020 [5]
ARB or BVMD	Autosomal recessive or Autosomal dominant	AAV2	Clinical trial	(Ongoing) Evaluate the safety and tolerability of drug OPGx-BEST1 in one eye for 5 years post-injection	Opus Genetics, Inc. 2025 [6]

*Adeno-associated virus serotype 2 (AAV2); calcium-dependent chloride channel (CaCC); induced pluripotent stem cell-derived (iPSC); photoreceptor (PR); retinal pigment epithelium (RPE).

Table 1: Preclinical and clinical studies investigating gene augmentation strategies for treating ARB and BVMD

By analyzing whole-cell patch clamp electrophysiology in patient-specific iPSC-RPE cells, Li et al. established that BEST1 disease-causing mutations impair Ca²⁺-dependent Cl⁻ currents in human RPE. Critically, Sinha et al. demonstrated that iPSC modeling can identify which dominant mutations respond to gene augmentation alone versus those requiring combined therapeutic approaches. In their study of three genotypically diverse dominant BVMD patient-derived iPSC-RPE cells, two responded to AAV-mediated gene augmentation alone, while one required CRISPR-mediated editing of the mutant allele to

achieve functional rescue. The importance of mutation-specific therapeutic strategies is evident, as is the potential role of patient-derived iPSC-RPE models as a predictive platform for personalized medicine.

OPGx-BEST1/BIRD-1 Clinical Trial

OPGx-BEST1 is an AAV2-based gene therapy designed to specifically treat ARB and BVMD. The therapeutic strategy relies on gene augmentation to compensate for defective BEST1 proteins by supplying a healthy, functional copy of the gene. AAV2 has demonstrated efficiency and safety in targeting the RPE cells, the primary site of the defect in these diseases. The vector is engineered to introduce a functional human BEST1 gene (hBEST1) into the RPE cells using an expression cassette that features a codon-optimized, full-length hBEST1 gene under the control of the vitelliform macular dystrophy 2 (VMD2) promoter; this promoter is crucial as it restricts gene expression specifically to the target RPE cells, ensuring safe and localized activity [1], [26].

In pre-clinical pharmacology and toxicology studies, OPGx-BEST1 was successfully administered to BEST1-mutant dogs (unpublished data). The treatment reduced the photoreceptor to RPE distance, and in some animals either prevented the onset of clinically detectable BEST1 lesions or caused preexisting areas of focal retinal detachment to reattach. Eyes treated with OPGx-BEST1 also had improved electroretinogram function compared to untreated eyes. No mortality, systemic toxicity, ocular toxicity, or test article-related effects on body/organ weight, clinical pathology parameters, or macroscopic/histopathologic findings were seen during the 13-week in-life phase of the study.

The BIRD-1 clinical trial is a Phase 1b/2a, open-label, dose-escalation basket study designed to assess the safety, tolerability, and preliminary efficacy of a single subretinal injection of OPGx-BEST1 [6]. The basket design enrolls both ARB and BVMD adult patients based on the recognition that both conditions predominantly involve loss-of-function mutations amenable to gene augmentation, regardless of inheritance pattern. Confirmation of mutations on chromosome 11q12-q13.1 by certified genetic testing is required for study enrollment. Two doses are proposed, with safety oversight managed by an Independent Data Monitoring Committee (IDMC) before dose escalation. Following the one-time injection, participants are monitored for 5 years to evaluate primary objectives (safe dose identification) and secondary objectives (immunogenicity and visual function efficacy via central reading center comparisons to baseline). Figure 5 is a schematic representation of the clinical trial study design.

ARB - Autosomal-Recessive Bestrophinopathy; BEST1 - Bestrophin-1; BVMD - Best vitelliform macular dystrophy; IDMC - Independent Data Monitoring Committee
 *Based on Cohort 1 data, IDMC will determine appropriateness of continuation to Cohort 2 and adjust the dose level as needed.

Figure 5. BIRD-1 Clinical Trial Design. BIRD-1 is a Phase 1b/2a, open-label, dose-escalation basket study designed to assess the safety, tolerability, and preliminary efficacy of a single subretinal injection of OPGx-BEST1.

CONCLUSION

Gene therapy represents a profound shift in the treatment landscape for inherited retinal diseases like BVMD and ARB, which currently lack therapeutic options. The success of gene augmentation for treating Leber congenital amaurosis makes this strategy particularly compelling for BEST1-related bestrophinopathies. However, a small subset of bestrophinopathies, most notably ADVIRC, cannot be rescued by wildtype supplementation alone. These cases require more complex strategies combining gene augmentation with allele-specific silencing or gene editing. By understanding the specific molecular mechanism of a pathogenic variant (loss-of-function, dominant-negative, or gain-of-function) rather than inheritance pattern alone, optimal gene therapy approaches can be personalized.

Patient-specific iPSC-RPE models have emerged as powerful tools for predicting mutation-specific responses to gene therapy, enabling personalized treatment approaches that match therapeutic strategy to individual patient mutations. The ongoing BIRD-1 clinical trial, which utilizes the novel OPGx-BEST1 AAV2 vector specifically engineered with the RPE-targeting VMD2 promoter to supply a healthy BEST1 gene, marks a critical step forward in translating the gene augmentation strategy into a clinical reality. This trial is designed to evaluate the safety of OPGx-BEST1 and to assess its potential for long-term vision stabilization in BVMD and ARB patients by targeting the common pathway of BEST1 deficiency that underlies the vast majority of bestrophinopathies.

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